

SUGAR: A Computer Vision Approach to Suture Quality Assessment

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INTRODUCTION

Suturing is a fundamental surgical skill, and educators meticulously evaluate surgical trainees' skills. The evaluation methods are direct observation and manual video review, which are highly resource-intensive and inevitably subjective. This paper describes the Surgical sUturing GrAdeR (SUGAR), a computer vision system that delivers objective and cost-effective assessments of suture quality. It allows students to reach basic proficiency using self-directed learning. Our results show the ability to automatically evaluate key quality parameters of suturing and the potential for its use as an educational tool, achieving a precision of 91.8% and a recall factor of 86.7%.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Background

Computer Vision (CV) based methods for evaluating surgical skills are faster, potentially less subjective and more reproducible, and require less trainer-hours [1]. Several studies have addressed how CV techniques enable the calculation of metrics based on suture images, and automate the evaluation of suturing skills based on sutures' performance, involving metrics of interest [2], [3], [4].

The one-stage YOLOv11 CV algorithm is considered a prominent object detection algorithm, being the selected algorithm for this project. This selection is also directly linked to YOLOv11's advanced instance segmentation capability, which delivers fine-grained, pixel-level object detection that delineates precise object boundaries [5].

For this Project, the CV algorithm involves two successive stages: 1) Image Processing and 2) Metrics Extraction. In the Image Processing stage, the CV algorithm uses advanced instance segmentation techniques to detect and identify key suture components: individual sutures, knots, wounds and leftovers. In the Metrics Extraction stage, the suture information is used to compute metrics for suture quality assessment.

Methodology

The SUGAR system focuses on interrupted sutures, a technique that uses non-connected stitches with a knot placed in each stitch and the leftover ends of the thread after the knot. To train, validate and test the SUGAR system, the Noraset et al.'s dataset [6] was obtained, containing 225 images (185 for training, 30 for validation, 10 for testing). This dataset presented images of suture practice end-products performed by novices and experts,

with manual annotations for training models and evaluating the system. Data augmentation techniques, such as cropping, rotation and brightness variation, were applied to the dataset, originating a dataset with 539 images (471 for training, 51 for validation, 17 for testing).

Analysis and Evaluation of Suture Quality Metrics

In the SUGAR Project, relevant suture quality metrics are analysed and evaluated to determine that:

- The location of each knot is the same relative to the wound and across the wound.
- The orientation of each stitch is approximately 90° to the wound.
- The skewness of angle (orientation of each stitch) is equal across the wound.
- The bite size (length of the stitch) is equal across the wound.
- The pitch size (distance between each stitch) is equal across the wound.
- The length of each leftover is equal throughout the sutures.
- The left bite size (interval distance between the stitch's left extremity and the wound) is equal across the wound.
- The right bite size (interval distance between the stitch's right extremity and the wound) is equal across the wound.

In addition, the overall suture symmetry and the overall suture quality are assessed through averaging of the aforementioned metrics. Indeed, the overall suture symmetry considers the uniformity of the left and right bite size, averaging the left and right bite size metrics and providing a perspective of overall uniformity. Lastly, the overall suture quality averages all the metrics' percentages, grading the analysed suture as inadequate (< 50%), adequate (< 70%), good (< 80%), very good (< 90%) and excellent ($\geq 90\%$), and thus completing the suture quality assessment. The quality assessment of sutures is therefore based on variables related with the sutures' size, symmetry and orientation.

RESULTS

Model Training and Validation

The SUGAR Project adopted instance segmentation to enable a precise analysis of suture quality metrics. The CV algorithm YOLOv11 was chosen and trained with the previously mentioned datasets. Based on the obtained results, the model selected for the Project's suture metrics

analysis displayed a 89.2% score, with a precision of 91.8% and a recall of 86.7%.

SUGAR System Validation

The suture quality analysis performed in the SUGAR system is the result of hardcoded software using the Python language. Code functions were created to calculate the length between two 2D points, the distance between two 1D points, the average of values in a vector, the stitch orientation and the wound orientation. To assess the suture's quality, the aforementioned metrics are analysed, with the overall suture quality representing the final grade.

Because the dataset provides images of suture end-products by novices and experts, an image of each suture was analysed visually by the author and by the designed system. Figures 1 and 2 present images of the suture end-products made by a novice and by an expert, respectively.

(a) Original novice's suture image. (b) Image produced with SUGAR's CV model.

Fig. 1: Comparison between the original novice suture image and the result of the SUGAR CV segmentation model.

(a) Original expert's suture image. (b) Image produced with SUGAR's CV model.

Fig. 2: Comparison between the original expert suture image and the result of the SUGAR CV segmentation model.

In Figure 1, the grades given to the novice are:

- Knot Placement: 16.67%
- Suture Orientation Quality: 100.00%
- Skewness of Angle: 90.91%
- Bite Size Quality: 16.67%

- Pitch Size Quality: 100.00%
- Leftover Size Quality: 83.33%
- Left Bite Size Quality: 100.00%
- Right Bite Size Quality: 40.00%
- Overall Suture Symmetry: 70.00%
- Overall Suture Quality: 68.45% (Adequate)

In Figure 2, the grades given to the expert are:

- Knot Placement: 100.00%
- Suture Orientation Quality: 60.00%
- Skewness of Angle: 88.89%
- Bite Size Quality: 80.00%
- Pitch Size Quality: 100.00%
- Leftover Size Quality: 100.00%
- Left Bite Size Quality: 100.00%
- Right Bite Size Quality: 75.00%
- Overall Suture Symmetry: 87.50%
- Overall Suture Quality: 87.99% (Very Good)

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The SUGAR system is capable of reliably detecting and identifying key suture components in interrupted sutures and extracting knot placement, suture orientation, skewness of angle, bite size, pitch size, leftover length, left bite size, right bite size, overall suture symmetry and overall suture quality metrics.

It is noted that using 2D images instead of 3D information, with its associated geometric inaccuracy, does not significantly impact the suturing evaluation. An exception would be the computation of the leftover size quality metric, namely for novices, as the leftover orientation tends to vary and 3D points would be helpful for the accurate determination of leftover size. Still, the metric's goal of pinpointing leftover consistency is achieved with the use of 2D images.

Overall, the SUGAR System exhibits promising results regarding the metrics' grading, distinguishing between the quality of sutures performed by a novice and an expert. Future work will focus on investigating the model's performance on video and/or real-time settings.

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